

1 **Supercritical anti-solvent fractionation for improving antioxidant and anti-**
2 **inflammatory activities of an *Achillea Millefolium* L. extract**

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23 **Abstract**

24 *Achillea millefolium* L. is a plant widely used in traditional medicine. Nowadays, there is
25 a growing concern about the study of its bioactive properties in order to develop food and
26 nutraceutical formulations. Supercritical anti-solvent fractionation (SAF) of an *A.*
27 *millefolium* extract was carried out to improve its antioxidant and anti-inflammatory
28 activities. A selective precipitation of phenolic compounds was achieved in the
29 precipitation vessel fractions, which presented an antioxidant activity twice than original
30 extract, especially when fractionation was carried out at 10 MPa. The main phenolic
31 components identified in this fraction were luteolin-7-*O*-glucoside, 3,5-dicaffeoylquinic
32 acid, 6-hydroxyluteolin-7-*O*-glucoside and apigenin-7-*O*-glucoside. However, separator
33 fractions presented higher anti-inflammatory activity than precipitation vessel ones,
34 particularly at 15 MPa. This fact could be related to separator fractions enrichment in
35 anti-inflammatory compounds, mainly camphor, artemisia ketone and borneol.
36 Therefore, SAF produced a concentration of antioxidant and anti-inflammatory
37 compounds that could be used as high-added valued ingredients.

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40 **Keywords:** supercritical anti-solvent fractionation, yarrow, antioxidant activity, anti-
41 inflammatory activity, phenolic compounds, bioactive ingredients.

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46 **Abbreviations:** SAF (Supercritical anti-solvent fractionation); DCQA (Dicaffeoylquinic
47 acid); SC-CO₂ (Supercritical CO₂); UAE (Ultrasound-Assisted extraction); GAE (Gallic
48 acid equivalents); THP-1/M (Human THP-1 monocytes differentiated to macrophages).

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50 **1. Introduction**

51 *Achillea millefolium* L. (yarrow) is a flowering plant widely used in folk medicine in
52 Europe. Aqueous and alcoholic extracts from dried upper parts of yarrow have been
53 employed in the treatment of digestive problems, hepato-biliary disorders and externally,
54 for the treatment of skin and mucous membrane inflammation (Dias et al., 2013). The
55 study of this plant, both its composition and biological activities, has awakened a growing
56 interest in order to develop pharmaceutical, food and nutraceutical products. Vitas,
57 Cvetanović, Mašković, Švarc-Gajić & Malbaša (2018) produced kombucha beverages
58 from a yarrow infusion and extracts. In addition, nowadays there are on the market several
59 herbal tea mixtures (containing yarrow), mainly indicated for digestive problems.

60 Certain naturally occurring bioactive compounds present in *A. millefolium*, such as
61 phenolic compounds, particularly chlorogenic and dicaffeoylquinic acids (DCQA) and
62 flavonoids, as well as those belonging to the volatile oil fraction have been associated
63 with health benefits (Mohammadhosseini, Sarker, & Akbarzadeh, 2017). Moreover,
64 recent reports indicated that *Achillea* genus presents an important antioxidant activity,
65 related to its flavonoids and total phenolic content (Giorgi, Mingozi, Madeo, Speranza,
66 & Cocucci, 2009; Mohammadhosseini et al., 2017). In addition, Trumbeckaite et al.
67 (2011) reported that the radical-scavenging properties of a hydroalcoholic extract of *A.*
68 *millefolium* were related to the presence of luteolin and chlorogenic acid in the extract, an
69 in a lesser extent, to the presence of rutin and luteolin-7-*O*-glucoside. *A. millefolium*
70 extracts have also been reported to present anti-inflammatory activity (Tadić et al., 2017).
71 Moreover, Kazemi (2015) showed that an *A. millefolium* essential oil, with high quantities
72 of thymol and borneol, was able to inhibit nitric oxide production in macrophages
73 stimulated with LPS (lipopolysaccharide).

74 Different approaches have been carried out in order to obtain fractions with high
75 concentrations of phenolic compounds or essential oils components than original plants
76 extracts; such as applying anion exchange resins (Kammerer, Boschet, Kammerer, &
77 Carle, 2011), high pressure techniques (Fernández-Ponce, Casas, Mantell, & de la Ossa,
78 2015), membrane separation (Cissé, Vaillant, Pallet, & Dornier, 2011), supercritical fluid
79 extraction with fractionation (Reverchon, & de Marco, 2006) or chromatography methods
80 (Pedan, Fischer, & Rohn, 2016; Shaheen, Lu, Geng, Shao & Wei, 2017). Recently,
81 supercritical anti-solvent fractionation (SAF) has been proposed for the fractionation of
82 complex plants extracts. In addition, the use of carbon dioxide as a supercritical fluid
83 offers many advantages, such as the low critical temperature of CO₂ and the absence of
84 oxygen during extraction, which allows minimize or avoid the degradation of solutes, as
85 well as the possibility of recovering a free-solvent fraction (Wijngaard, Hossain, Rai, &
86 Brunton, 2012). In the SAF process, a polar liquid solution of a plant extract, containing
87 several families of compounds, is sprayed continuously in a co-current with supercritical
88 CO₂ (SC-CO₂), which acts as antisolvent. This contact allows the precipitation of more
89 polar components from the liquid solution, insoluble in SC-CO₂, whereas the remaining
90 compounds, that are mainly less polar components, remained dissolved and are recovered
91 by downstream pressure reduction (Meneses, Caputo, Scognamiglio, Reverchon, &
92 Adami, 2015).

93 For that matter, SAF technique has recently used to fractionate phenolic compounds from
94 plants extracts. Therefore, Natolino, Da Porto, Rodríguez-Rojo, Moreno & Cocero (2016)
95 used this technique to obtain fractions enriched in polyphenols from a grape marc extract.
96 Operating at 12MPa, 45 °C and 0.99 CO₂ molar fraction, they obtained fractions with a
97 relative enrichment of 350% of total polyphenols and a proanthocyanidins enrichment
98 between 300-450%. Visentín, Cismondi, & Maestri (2011) also applied the SAF to

99 improve carnosic acid (CA) recovery from an ethanolic extract of rosemary leaves,
100 obtaining two different fractions, one insoluble with low concentration in CA (<5%) and
101 another resinous extract with 33% of CA. Moreover, Villanueva et al. (2015) carried out
102 the fractionation of green tea extracts obtaining decaffeinated fractions with high
103 concentration in catechins.

104 Nevertheless, there are only few studies relating the enrichment in phenolic compounds
105 or essential oil components of the fractions obtained by this technique, with their
106 biological activities. Chinnarasu et al. (2015) obtained precipitates with high antioxidant
107 activity from the fractionation of olive leaves extracts and Marqués, Porta, Reverchon,
108 Renuncio and Mainar (2013) concentrated antioxidants from a defatted grape seed waste
109 extract, achieving concentrations up to 2.7 higher than those in the starting solution.
110 Sánchez-Camargo et al. (2016) also enhanced the antiproliferative activity of a rosemary
111 fraction enriched in carnosic acid and carnosol.

112 In this context, and based on a previous work (Villanueva-Bermejo et al., 2017), the aim
113 of the present study was to improve the antioxidant and anti-inflammatory activities of an
114 *A. millefolium* extract using SAF technology. Besides, the original extract and fractions
115 obtained were analyzed in order to relate its chemical composition with the biological
116 activities found.

117

118 **2. Materials and methods**

119 2.1. Reagents and chemicals

120 Ethanol (99.5% purity) and Folin-Ciocalteu's reagent were obtained from Panreac
121 (Barcelona, Spain). (±)-6-Hydroxy-2,5,7,8-tetramethylchromane-2-carboxylic acid
122 (Trolox), 2,2'-Azino-bis (3-ethylbenzothiazoline-6-sulfonic acid) diammonium salt
123 (ABTS), gallic acid for titration (> 97.5%), potassium persulfate (99.9%) and thiazolyl

124 blue tetrazolium bromide (MTT) were purchased from Sigma Aldrich (Madrid, Spain).
125 Formic acid (99%) was obtained from Acros Organics (Madrid, Spain) and acetonitrile
126 HPLC grade from Macron Fine Chemicals (Madrid, Spain). Reference standards for
127 phenolic compounds, such as chlorogenic acid, cryptochlorogenic acid, diosmetin, ferulic
128 acid, neochlorogenic acid, rosmarinic acid and vitexin (all analytical standard or HPLC
129 purity $\geq 95\%$) were purchased from Sigma Aldrich (Madrid, Spain). 1,5-Dicaffeoylquinic
130 acid (DCQA), 3,4-DCQA, 3,5-DCQA, 4,5-DCQA, apigenin, caftaric acid, casticin,
131 luteolin, orientin, schaftoside and vicenin II were obtained from Phytolab (Madrid,
132 Spain). Finally, amentoflavone, apigenin-7-*O*-glucoside, caffeic acid, homoorientin,
133 luteolin-7-*O*- β -D-glucoside, quercetin and rutin were obtained from Extrasynthese S.A.
134 (Genay, France) and luteolin-7-*O*- β -D-glucuronide from HWI Analytic GmbH
135 (Rülzheim, Germany). The water used in this study was ultrapure type 1 (Millipore,
136 Madrid, Spain). CO₂ (N38) was purchased from Carbueros Metalicos (Madrid, Spain).

137

138 2.2. Yarrow samples and Ultrasound-Assisted Extraction (UAE)

139 *A. millefolium* from Bulgaria was supplied by a local herbalist (Murcia, Spain). According
140 to supplier specifications, the sample included inflorescences and upper dried leaves of
141 the plant (harvested in spring) and sun-dried (water content < than 5% wt). The plant was
142 ground using a Premill 250 hammer mill (Leal S.A., Granollers, Spain) and sieved
143 (particle size < 500 μm). UAE plant extraction was carried out by using an ultrasonic
144 device (Branson Digital Sonifier 250, Danbury, USA) with a power of 200 W and
145 frequencies of 60 kHz. Extraction conditions employed were ethanol as extraction solvent
146 (1:10 plant/solvent ratio), 30 min time, 40 °C temperature and an output of 70% with
147 respect to the nominal amplitude. Finally, the extract was concentrated, until the final

148 volume contained 17.9 mg/mL of total solid concentration (2.3% wt.) by rotary
149 evaporation and stored at $-20\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ until its use in the SAF process.

150

151 2.3. SAF process

152 A detailed explanation of the device and the process design employed can be found
153 elsewhere (Villanueva-Bermejo et al., 2017). Briefly, fractionation of UAE yarrow
154 solution (concentration of 17.9 mg/mL) was carried out at two different pressures (10 and
155 15 MPa), $40\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ and CO_2 /extract flow ratio of 31.3 g/g (50 g/min for CO_2 and 1.6 g/min
156 for UAE extract). The experiment started by pumping SC- CO_2 into the precipitation
157 vessel until the pressure and temperature conditions were attained. Then, the UAE yarrow
158 solution was pumped into the precipitator. After mixing, the yarrow extract components
159 that were not soluble in SC- CO_2 + ethanol mixture precipitated in the precipitation vessel
160 and were collected (precipitation vessel fraction). The fraction soluble in SC- CO_2 +
161 ethanol went to separators where reduced pressure turned CO_2 into a gas and this fraction
162 together with ethanol was also collected. The samples obtained in both separators were
163 combined in a single fraction and ethanol removed by rotary evaporation under vacuum
164 (separator fraction). Fractions were kept at $-20\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ under darkness until analysis.

165

166 2.4. HPLC-PAD-ESI-QTOF-MS analysis

167 Phenolic compounds were analyzed by HPLC following the chromatographic method
168 developed by Villalva et al. (2018). An Agilent HPLC 1260 Infinity series system
169 (Agilent Technologies Inc., Santa Clara, CA, USA) was used for that purpose.
170 Chromatographic separation was carried out by using a reverse phase ACE Excell 3 Super
171 C18 column (150 mm x 4.6 mm, 3 μm particle size) from Advanced Chromatography
172 Technologies (Aberdeen, Scotland) protected by an ACE 3 C18-AR (10 mm x 3 mm)

173 guard column. Dry samples were dissolved in ethanol to reach a 5 mg/mL concentration
174 and filtered by 0.45 μm polyvinylidene fluoride (PVDF) filter before injection (20 μL).
175 Retention time and UV-Vis spectrum of each chromatographic peak was compared with
176 analytical standards for identification purpose; moreover, accurate mass from HPLC-ESI-
177 QTOF-MS in negative mode analysis was used for compounds assignment.
178 Compounds quantification was carried out by using calibration curves from analytical
179 standard, as previously described in Villalva et al. (2018). In addition, luteolin-6,8-di-*C*-
180 glucoside, 6-hydroxyluteolin-7-*O*-glucoside and non-identified flavones were quantified
181 by the calibration curve of orientin, luteolin-7-*O*-glucoside and luteolin respectively.
182 Likewise, schaftoside and vicenin II calibration curves were used for schaftoside isomer
183 and apigenin-*C*-hexoside-*C*-pentoside quantification.

184 2.5. GC-MS analysis of the separator fractions

185 The analysis of the UAE extract and SAF fractions collected from the separator was
186 carried out in an Agilent 7890A system (Agilent Technologies, Santa Clara, CA, USA).
187 The unit comprised a split/splitless injector, a FID detector and a mass spectrometer
188 detector (5975C triple-axis). The analysis was performed using an Agilent HP-5MS
189 capillary column (30 m \times 0.25 mm i.d., 0.25 μm phase thickness) and the following
190 chromatographic method: 40 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ initial temperature, from 40 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ to 150 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ at 3 $^{\circ}\text{C min}^{-1}$,
191 isothermal at 150 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ for 10 min, then increased from 150 to 300 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ at 6 $^{\circ}\text{C min}^{-1}$ and
192 finally isothermal at 300 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ for 1 min. Samples were dissolved in ethanol (at 5 mg/mL),
193 filtered by 0.45 μm filters and injected (1 μL) in splitless mode. Helium (99.99 %) was
194 employed as carrier gas (1 mL/min flow rate). The temperatures used were 250 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ for the
195 injector and 230, 280 and 150 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ for the mass spectrometer ion source, interface and
196 quadrupole, respectively. The mass spectrometer operated under electron impact mode
197 (70 eV) and it was used in total ion current (TIC) mode (mass range from 40 to 500 m/z).

198 The identification of compounds was performed by matching the mass spectral
199 fragmentation patterns with the Wiley 229 mass spectral library, as well as comparing
200 their corresponding retention index to those reported in the literature. Analyses were
201 done in triplicate.

202

203 2.6. Determination of total phenolic content (TPC) and antioxidant activity

204 TPC determination was carried out according to Folin-Ciocalteu reagent method as
205 described by Singleton, Orthofer & Lamuela-Reventos (1999) using gallic acid as
206 standard. In brief, 10 μ l of samples (5 mg/mL for all samples, except for P10 and P15
207 which working solution was 3 mg/mL) were mixed with 50 μ L of Folin-Ciocalteu
208 reagent and 790 μ L of deionized water. After 3 min, 150 μ L of sodium carbonate solution
209 (20% w/v) were added and mixed. After 2h, the absorbance at 760 nm was recorded. The
210 results were expressed as mg of gallic acid equivalents (GAE)/g dry sample. Analyses
211 were performed at least in triplicate.

212 The antioxidant activity was measured using the ABTS⁺ radical scavenging assay as
213 described in Re et al. (1999). The reaction was placed with 990 μ L of the diluted ABTS⁺
214 radical solution and 10 μ L of plant extract dilutions in order to achieve a 20% to 80% of
215 radical inhibition (sample concentration varying from 5 mg/mL to 20 mg/mL). The
216 reaction was allowed to stand until the absorbance reached a plateau, and the absorbance
217 was recorded at 734 nm. Results were expressed as mmol Trolox equivalent/g dry sample
218 (TEAC value). Analyses were done at least in triplicate.

219

220 2.7. Anti-inflammatory activity

221 Human THP-1 monocytes (ATCC, Manassas, VA, USA) were plated at a density of
222 5×10^5 cells/mL in 24 wells plates. Culture medium consisted in RPMI 1640 supplemented

223 with 10% FBS, 100 U/mL penicillin, 100 mg/mL streptomycin, 2 mM L-glutamine
224 (Gibco, Paisley, UK) and 0.05 mM β -mercaptoethanol (Sigma-Aldrich, Madrid, Spain)
225 at 37 °C in 95% humidified air containing 5% CO₂. Monocytes differentiation to
226 macrophages (THP-1/M cells) was induced by maintaining the cells with 100 ng/ml of
227 phorbol 12-myristate 13-acetate (PMA) (Sigma-Aldrich, Madrid, Spain) for 48 h. THP-
228 1/M cells viability, in presence of yarrow extract or fractions, was tested by MTT assay
229 following Mosmann (1983) method. The assays were performed in triplicate.
230 After differentiation, THP-1/M cells were washed with PBS and incubated with 0.05
231 μ g/mL of LPS from E. Coli O55:B5 (Sigma-Aldrich, Spain) in presence of yarrow extract
232 or fractions for 24 h. Then, the supernatants were collected and frozen at -20 °C. An anti-
233 inflammatory drug, indomethacin (5 μ g/mL), was used as a reference.
234 ELISA kits (BD Biosciences, Aalst, Belgium), according to manufacturer's instructions,
235 were used to measure the release of TNF- α , IL-1 β and IL-6 in the supernatants of THP-
236 1/M cells. The quantification was carried out at 450 nm with substrate correction at 570
237 nm using a multiscanner autoreader (InfiniteM200 Tecan, Barcelona, Spain). The results
238 were expressed as the mean of three determinations \pm standard deviation.

239

240 2.8. Statistical analysis

241 Statistical analysis was performed using Statgraphics v. Centurion XVI package for
242 Windows (Statpoint Inc., Warrenton, VA, USA). Statistical differences between samples
243 were analyzed by one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) and Fisher's least significant
244 difference (LSD) procedure was applied to determine significant differences between
245 means at $p \leq 0.05$.

246

247 3. Results and discussion

248 **3.1. TPC content and antioxidant activity of yarrow extract and SAF fractions.**

249 UAE extracts from yarrow were carried out using ethanol as extraction solvent, at 40 °C
250 and 30 min. Previous studies carried out in the research group (data not shown) showed
251 that those conditions were the most appropriated to obtain extracts with a high content of
252 TPC and an important antioxidant activity. Thus, this UAE extract (called original
253 extract) presented a yield of $5.7 \pm 0.9\%$ (% dry wt.), a TPC of 54.30 ± 1.07 mg GAE/g
254 extract and a TEAC value of 0.173 ± 0.004 mmol Trolox/g extract.

255 SAF process was carried out in order to enhance the antioxidant activity of this extract.
256 Consequently, two different experiments, at 10 and 15 MPa of pressure, 40 °C and
257 CO₂/extract flow ratio of 31.3 g/g, were developed. These conditions were based in a
258 previous work (Villanueva-Bermejo et al., 2017).

259 Fractions obtained at 10 and 15 MPa from the precipitation vessel (called P10 and P15)
260 and separators (called S10 and S15) were collected and its yield value, TPC content and
261 antioxidant activity were determined (Table 1). Results indicated that SAF process
262 achieved an important phenolic compounds enrichment in the precipitation vessel
263 fractions. It is worth to mention that this enrichment was significantly higher when used
264 pressure was 10 MPa, where P10 fraction presented an antioxidant activity 2-fold superior
265 than the original extract. Regarding separator fractions, S10 and S15 showed a similar
266 antioxidant activity and near 5-fold lower than original extract. This result was related to
267 the lower quantity of TPC presented in these fractions.

268 Therefore, phenolic composition of the original extract and fractions were analyzed in
269 order to establish a relationship between its composition and the antioxidant activity
270 found.

271

272 **3.2. Phenolic characterization of yarrow extract and SAF fractions.**

273 The HPLC analysis of phenolic compounds in the original extract and SAF fractions are
274 shown in Table 2. The main compounds identified in the original extract were flavonoids,
275 either in glycosylated or in aglycone form, and phenolic acids. Therefore, the compounds
276 presented in higher concentration corresponded to the flavonoids luteolin and its
277 glycosylated form (luteolin-7-*O*-glucoside), as well as the dicaffeoylquinic acids, where
278 the 3,5-DCQA stood out. These results are in agreement with others previously
279 reported, where the main flavonoids found in several yarrow extracts were luteolin-7-*O*-
280 glucoside, luteolin, apigenin-7-*O*-glucoside and apigenin, while within the
281 dicaffeoylquinic acids, 3,5-DCQA was the one in a greater extent (Benedek, Gjoncaj,
282 Saukei, & Kopp, 2007; Vitalini et al., 2011). Related to precipitation vessel fractions, its
283 principal components were luteolin-7-*O*-glucoside, 3,5-DCQA, luteolin, apigenin-7-*O*-
284 glucoside and 6-hydroxyluteolin-7-*O*-glucoside, representing between 73% (P10) and
285 60% (P15) of all phenolic compounds identified. Meanwhile, separator fractions
286 contained a reduced quantity of phenolic compounds, where flavonoids aglycones
287 stood out.

288 Precipitation vessel fractions and the original sample presented a similar phenolic
289 composition, although the compounds concentration in the fractions was, in general,
290 much higher, highlighting luteolin-7-*O*-glucoside and 3,5-DCQA. These results could be
291 related to the low solubility of glycosylated flavonoids and phenolic acids in the SC-CO₂
292 + ethanol mixture, since these compounds are poorly soluble in low-polar solvents
293 (Chebil et al., 2007). On the other hand, the flavonoids aglycones, as less polar
294 compounds, would be more soluble in the mixture SC-CO₂ + ethanol and therefore they
295 would be dragged to the separator fraction.

296 However, it should be noted that there were some differences between fractions P10 and
297 P15, since P10 fraction presented a greater amount of luteolin-7-*O*-glucoside and 3,5-

298 DCQA than P15 fraction, whereas P15 contained a higher quantity of luteolin and
299 apigenin than P10. These results could indicate that an increase in pressure during the
300 fractionation process, would increment the presence of aglycones in the precipitation
301 vessel fraction. In order to explain these results, it must be taken into account the complex
302 multicomponent structure of extracts, comprising substances in a wide polarity range and
303 with different solubility in SC-CO₂, which could exert a strong effect regarding the partial
304 solubility of compounds involved and their precipitation behavior. Nevertheless,
305 observing the solubility behavior of pure compounds in SC-CO₂, it can be established
306 that in the case of more polar compounds (e.g. hydroxycinnamic acids) an increase of
307 pressure from 10 to 15 MPa resulted in 4.4-5.4 solubility increase (Murga, Sanz, Beltran
308 & Cabeza, 2003), while for less polar compounds (e.g. quercetin) this ratio was about 3.0-
309 3.5 (Chafer, Fornari, Berna & Stateva, 2004). Thus, according to the pure component
310 solubility behavior, an increase of the precipitation pressure could increase the recovery
311 of aglycones in precipitation vessel.

312 Thus, the higher antioxidant activity found in P10 and P15, compared to original extract,
313 could be related with the significant increase in several phenolic compounds found in
314 these fractions, mainly luteolin-7-*O*-glucoside, 3,5-DCQA, luteolin (only in P15),
315 apigenin-7-*O*-glucoside and 6-hydroxyluteolin-7-*O*-glucoside. Besides, when comparing
316 P10 and P15, it can be observed that P10, with the higher antioxidant activity, also
317 presented the higher quantity of luteolin-7-*O*-glucoside and 3,5-DCQA (representing
318 almost 55% of the fraction). Kim et al. (2011) indicated that 3,5-DCQA presented an
319 important antioxidant activity, significantly higher than chlorogenic acid. Besides, the
320 antioxidant activity of luteolin-7-*O*-glucoside have also been reported (Song & Park,
321 2014; Antonisamy et al., 2016). However, it must be taken into account that this fact
322 could be also due to synergies among all the phenolic compounds found in P10 fraction.

323

324 **3.3. Anti-inflammatory activity of yarrow extract and SAF fractions.**

325 First, original extract and SAF fractions were evaluated for cytotoxicity on THP-1/M cells
326 by MTT method. Results showed that, at the higher concentration used in the anti-
327 inflammatory assays, 10 $\mu\text{g/mL}$, neither original extract nor SAF fractions presented
328 cytotoxicity (cell viability $\geq 95\%$). Indomethacin at 5 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ also presented no
329 cytotoxicity.

330 The activation of THP-1/M was carried out with the addition of LPS to the medium. Fig.
331 1 showed that these LPS treated cells (positive control), after an incubation period of 24h,
332 presented an important increase in the release of TNF- α , IL-1 β and IL-6, compared to
333 non-activated controls (negative control). When THP-1/M were activated with LPS in
334 presence of 5 and 10 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ of original extract and SAF fractions, a decrease in TNF- α
335 secreted level was observed (Fig. 1), compared with positive control. Moreover, 5 $\mu\text{g/mL}$
336 of original extract inhibited TNF- α secretion in a 40%. Regarding P10 and P15 fractions,
337 P15 presented a decrease in TNF- α superior to P10 and similar to that obtained with
338 original extract. However, it should be noted that the greatest decrease in TNF- α secretion
339 was achieved in presence of S10 and S15 fractions. Thus, 5 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ of S15 fraction
340 reduced TNF- α release in a 70%.

341 In the same way, the original extract and SAF fractions inhibited the IL-1 β secretion by
342 activated cells, at both concentrations employed, although separator fractions showed the
343 greatest inhibition (Fig. 1). Thus, meanwhile 10 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ of original extract decrease IL-1 β
344 release in a 40%, the same concentration of S15 showed an inhibition near to 70%. In
345 addition, 5 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ of S15 reduced IL-1 β secretion by a 60%. The obtained results for the
346 IL-6 release in presence of samples (Fig. 1) were similar to those obtained for TNF- α and

347 IL-1 β , since S10 and S15 fractions were the most active and produced an important
348 decrease in the IL-6 release (near to basal levels).

349 These results indicated that all SAF fractions presented anti-inflammatory activity,
350 although separator fractions were much more active than precipitation vessel ones. The
351 anti-inflammatory activity of precipitation vessel fractions could be related to its content
352 in phenolic compounds, more specifically with dicaffeoylquinic acids, luteolin, apigenin
353 and its glycosides, since the anti-inflammatory effects of these compounds have been
354 previously described (Liang & Kitts, 2016; Wang et al, 2014; Wang et al., 2017).
355 Moreover, Francisco et al. (2014) indicated that luteolin-7-*O*-glucoside presented a
356 certain anti-inflammatory activity, but lower than that observed with the luteolin aglycone
357 in LPS-stimulated macrophages. Similarly, Choi et al. (2014) reported that apigenin
358 presented higher anti-inflammatory activity than other naturally occurring *C*-glycosylated
359 derivatives of apigenin. These results could explain the higher inhibition of TNF- α , IL-
360 1 β and IL-6 secretion found when using P15 compared with P10, since P15 contained a
361 higher amount of luteolin and apigenin aglycones, whereas P10 presented a higher
362 quantity of luteolin-7-*O*-glucoside and apigenin-7-*O*-glucoside.

363 However, the higher anti-inflammatory activity found in separator fractions, could not be
364 related to its phenolic compounds content, due to the low quantity of these compounds
365 presented in these fractions. Thereby, it's relevant to notice that conditions used to obtain
366 the separator fractions allowed the enhancement of these fractions in essential oil
367 components. Since essential oils from *A. millefolium* have been reported to present anti-
368 inflammatory activity (Chou, Peng, Hsu, Lin & Shih, 2013; Kazemi, 2015), S10 and S15
369 were analyzed by GC-MS in order to establish a relationship between the composition
370 and the anti-inflammatory activity of these fractions.

371

372 **3.4. GC-MS characterization of separator fractions**

373 In order to identify the compounds involved in the anti-inflammatory activity found in
374 separator fractions (S10 and S15), a characterization by GC-MS of these fractions, along
375 with the original extract was performed. The identification of the main volatile
376 compounds presented in the sample (Table 3) was performed based on the comparison of
377 their mass spectra and retention index (RI). As can be observed, 30 identified and 2 non-
378 identified compounds were found in S10 and S15. In general, a very similar GC-MS
379 profile was obtained for both fractions, being camphor, artemisia ketone, borneol and 2,6-
380 dimethyl-1,7-octadiene-3,6-diol the most abundant compounds in both fractions. Original
381 yarrow extract also presented a similar profile to S10 and S15, although total
382 chromatographic area (expressed as Σ AUC) was much higher for the fractions. As
383 expected, separator fractions have been enriched in essential oil components (1.75 times
384 for S10 and 2.18 for S15), in comparison to the original extract. Regarding main
385 components, camphor and borneol were shown to reduce TNF- α , IL-1 β and IL-6
386 secretion in THP-1 macrophages stimulated with LPS or ox-LDL (oxidized low-density
387 lipoproteins) (Arranz et al., 2014a; Arranz et al., 2014b). Similarly, Rungqu et al. (2016)
388 reported that an essential oil containing a 37.5% of artemisia ketone presented an
389 important anti-inflammatory activity, evaluated in rats, using egg albumin-induced paw
390 edema. Therefore, the anti-inflammatory activity exhibited by S10 and S15 fractions
391 could be mainly related to the presence of these three compounds (camphor, borneol and
392 artemisia ketone) that represented approximately 30% of the fractions. However, the
393 contribution to other anti-inflammatory compounds presented in smaller quantities, such
394 as eucalyptol and β -linalool, to this activity cannot be ruled out. Thus, the enrichment of
395 S10 and S15 fractions in compounds that exhibit anti-inflammatory activity, regarding to
396 the original extract, would explain the higher anti-inflammatory activity of these

397 fractions. Accordingly, S15 fraction that presented a higher enrichment in essential oil
398 compounds than S10, also presented a higher anti-inflammatory activity.

399

400 **Conclusion**

401 Supercritical anti-solvent fractionation of an ethanolic yarrow extract resulted an
402 adequate method to improve its antioxidant and anti-inflammatory activities. Thus, a
403 selective precipitation of phenolic compounds increased its antioxidant activity twice,
404 compared to original extract, especially when fractionation was carried out at 10 MPa.
405 Regarding anti-inflammatory activity, separator fractions presented higher anti-
406 inflammatory activity than precipitation vessel ones. This fact was related to separator
407 fractions enrichment in essential oil compounds with anti-inflammatory activity. Being
408 more active, in this case, the separator fraction obtained when pressure was 15 MPa.
409 Therefore, this study pointed out the feasibility of SAF process as a green technology in
410 order to achieve a fractionation of compounds with different biological activities. This
411 fact could be a useful tool for food or nutraceutical products design.

412

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417

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601 **Table 1.** Yield values (mass precipitated/mass of solid pumped), TPC content and
 602 antioxidant activity (TEAC value) in original extract and SAF fractions: P10
 603 (precipitation vessel fraction at 10 MPa), P15 (precipitation vessel fraction at 15 MPa,
 604 S10 (separator fraction at 10 MPa) and S15 (separator fraction at 15 MPa). Data shown
 605 represents mean \pm S.D. (n=3).

Sample	Yield (%)	TPC (mg GAE/g)	TEAC value (mmol Trolox/g)
Original extract	5.7 \pm 0.9	54.30 \pm 1.07 ^c	0.173 \pm 0.004 ^c
P-10	6.6 \pm 1.1	136.44 \pm 1.28 ^a	0.345 \pm 0.002 ^a
S-10	52.1 \pm 5.3	30.30 \pm 0.25 ^d	0.035 \pm 0.002 ^d
P-15	13.3 \pm 2.4	119.20 \pm 2.23 ^b	0.317 \pm 0.003 ^b
S-15	42.6 \pm 4.2	23.83 \pm 0.85 ^e	0.033 \pm 0.002 ^d

606 ^{a,b,c,d,e} Different superscript letters denote statistical differences between samples within
 607 the same column. Significance level at $p \leq 0.05$ with Fisher's Least Significant
 608 Difference (LSD) test.

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620 **Table 2.** Phenolic composition of original extract and SAF fractions (mg compound/g
621 dry fraction). P10 (precipitation vessel fraction at 10 MPa), P15 (precipitation vessel
622 fraction at 15 MPa), S10 (separator fraction at 10 MPa) and S15 (separator fraction at 15
623 MPa). Data shown represents mean \pm S.D. (n=3).

Compound	Original	P-10	S-10	P-15	S-15
Neochlorogenic acid	0.06 \pm 0.00	0.18 \pm 0.00 ^{*a}	-	0.14 \pm 0.00 ^{*b}	-
Caftaric acid	< L.Q.	0.18 \pm 0.00 ^{*b}	-	0.22 \pm 0.00 ^{*a}	-
Chlorogenic acid	0.62 \pm 0.00	2.32 \pm 0.0 ^{*a}	0.10 \pm 0.00 [*]	1.91 \pm 0.04 ^{*b}	-
Cryptochlorogenic acid	0.01 \pm 0.01	0.03 \pm 0.00 ^a	-	0.04 \pm 0.01 ^a	-
Vicenin II	0.37 \pm 0.01	1.61 \pm 0.00 ^{*a}	-	1.12 \pm 0.01 ^{*b}	-
Caffeic acid	0.17 \pm 0.00	-	0.19 \pm 0.00 ^{*A}	-	0.18 \pm 0.00 ^{*B}
Schaftoside isomer	0.26 \pm 0.00	1.49 \pm 0.05 ^{*a}	-	0.90 \pm 0.00 ^{*b}	-
Schaftoside	0.27 \pm 0.00	1.36 \pm 0.00 ^{*a}	-	0.89 \pm 0.00 ^{*b}	-
Homoorientin	0.02 \pm 0.01	0.32 \pm 0.00 ^{*a}	-	0.16 \pm 0.00 ^{*b}	-
Apigenin-C-hexoside -C-pentoside	0.30 \pm 0.00	1.43 \pm 0.01 ^{*a}	-	0.85 \pm 0.00 ^{*b}	-
Luteolin-6,8-di-C-glucoside	0.47 \pm 0.00	2.39 \pm 0.01 ^{*a}	-	1.51 \pm 0.00 ^{*b}	-
6-hydroxyluteolin-7-O-glucoside	1.45 \pm 0.01	7.65 \pm 0.02 ^{*a}	0.02 \pm 0.00 [*]	4.66 \pm 0.00 ^{*b}	-
Rutin	0.51 \pm 0.01	1.44 \pm 0.00 ^{*a}	-	1.34 \pm 0.02 ^{*b}	-
Vitexin	0.13 \pm 0.01	0.15 \pm 0.00 ^{*b}	-	0.25 \pm 0.01 ^{*a}	-
Luteolin-7-O-glucoside	7.69 \pm 0.08	33.2 \pm 0.07 ^{*a}	0.39 \pm 0.00 [*]	23.9 \pm 0.97 ^{*b}	-
Luteolin-7-B-glucuronide	0.20 \pm 0.01	0.56 \pm 0.00 ^{*a}	-	0.59 \pm 0.03 ^{*a}	-
Ferulic acid	0.08 \pm 0.02	0.09 \pm 0.00 ^{*a}	-	0.04 \pm 0.00 ^{*b}	-
3,4-DCQA	0.38 \pm 0.05	1.23 \pm 0.00 ^{*a}	-	0.69 \pm 0.00 ^{*b}	-
1,5-DCQA	0.69 \pm 0.01	2.86 \pm 0.01 ^{*a}	-	1.80 \pm 0.09 ^{*b}	-
3,5-DCQA	3.62 \pm 0.02	17.8 \pm 0.03 ^{*a}	0.28 \pm 0.01 ^{*A}	11.6 \pm 0.10 ^{*b}	0.10 \pm 0.00 ^{*B}
Apigenin-7-O-glucoside	1.79 \pm 0.01	6.89 \pm 0.03 ^{*a}	0.32 \pm 0.00 [*]	5.88 \pm 0.01 ^{*b}	-
4,5-DCQA	0.97 \pm 0.01	4.30 \pm 0.01 ^{*a}	0.05 \pm 0.00 [*]	3.19 \pm 0.00 ^{*b}	-
Rosmarinic acid	0.18 \pm 0.00	-	-	-	-
Luteolin	4.47 \pm 0.01	4.58 \pm 0.01 ^{*b}	3.18 \pm 0.00 ^{*A}	13.0 \pm 0.00 ^{*a}	0.95 \pm 0.01 ^{*B}
Quercetin	0.47 \pm 0.00	0.68 \pm 0.00 ^{*b}	0.32 \pm 0.01 [*]	1.44 \pm 0.01 ^{*a}	-
Flavone n.i.	1.66 \pm 0.00	1.15 \pm 0.00 ^{*b}	1.42 \pm 0.00 ^{*A}	3.33 \pm 0.00 ^{*a}	1.16 \pm 0.00 ^{*B}
Apigenin	1.96 \pm 0.00	1.00 \pm 0.00 ^{*b}	1.83 \pm 0.00 ^{*A}	4.74 \pm 0.00 ^{*a}	0.93 \pm 0.00 ^{*B}
Diosmetin	0.50 \pm 0.00	0.31 \pm 0.00 ^{*b}	0.53 \pm 0.00 ^{*A}	0.73 \pm 0.00 ^{*a}	0.50 \pm 0.00 ^{*B}
Amentoflavone	0.42 \pm 0.00	0.16 \pm 0.00 ^{*b}	0.52 \pm 0.00 ^{*B}	0.41 \pm 0.00 ^{*a}	0.62 \pm 0.00 ^{*A}
Flavone n.i.	2.14 \pm 0.00	0.57 \pm 0.00 ^{*a}	2.68 \pm 0.00 ^{*B}	0.57 \pm 0.00 ^{*a}	3.68 \pm 0.00 ^{*A}
Casticin	0.29 \pm 0.00	-	0.44 \pm 0.01 ^{*B}	-	0.62 \pm 0.01 ^{*A}

624 < L.Q.: below limit of quantification. * An asterisk indicates statistical differences between
625 original extract and fractions. ^{a,b} Different lowercase letters denote statistical differences
626 between P10 and P15 fractions. ^{A,B} Different capital letters denote statistical differences
627 between S10 and S15 fractions. Significance level at $p \leq 0.05$ with Fisher's Least
628 Significant Difference (LSD) test.

Table 3. GC-MS identification, peak area contribution (%), and retention index (RI) of compounds found in original extract and separator fractions. S10 (separator fraction at 10 MPa) and S15 (separator fraction at 15 MPa).

RI	Compound	Original	S10	S15
997	Yomogi alcohol	2.1	2.0	2.2
1028	Eucalyptol	4.3	3.5	3.4
1037	γ -Vinyl- γ -valerolactone	1.8	1.6	1.5
1058	Artemisia ketone	11.0	9.9	9.4
1070	1,2-Epoxylinool	0.9	0.8	0.8
1079	Artemisia alcohol	1.0	0.8	0.8
1084	<i>cis</i> -Linalool oxide	0.8	0.6	0.7
1099	β -Linalool	0.9	0.9	0.9
1136	Camphor	13.8	12.5	12.3
1141	<i>cis</i> -Verbenol	0.9	0.7	0.7
1160	Borneol	8.7	8.9	8.6
1171	2-Methyl-2-octen-4-ol	1.0	0.9	1.0
1174	Terpinene-4-ol	0.5	0.4	0.5
1182	<i>p</i> -Cymen-8-ol	0.7	0.8	0.9
1188	3,7-dimethyl-1,5-Octadiene-3,7-diol	5.9	6.1	6.2
1200	Verbenone	0.5	0.6	0.6
1212	Fragranol	0.4	0.4	0.4
1218	2-Hydroxycineole	0.6	0.6	0.7
1236	<i>trans</i> -Chrysanthenyl acetate	2.4	2.5	2.5
1250	Piperitone	0.9	0.9	1.0
1261	(<i>5E</i>)-5,9-Dimethyl-5,8-decadien-2-one	1.5	1.4	1.3
1276	2,6-Dimethyl-1,7-octadiene-3,6-diol	8.6	9.3	9.3
1280	Bornyl acetate	0.8	1.0	1.0
1284	n.i.	7.2	8.7	8.5
1393	Jasmone	1.6	1.6	1.5
1412	β -Caryophyllene	1.4	1.6	1.5
1569	Spathulenol	0.9	1.2	1.1
1578	Caryophyllene oxide	4.9	6.0	5.8
1640	β -Eudesmol	1.2	1.2	1.5
1810	Saussurea lactone	3.4	3.2	3.2
1845	Hexahydrofarnesyl acetone	3.0	3.2	3.4
2069	n.i.	6.5	6.2	6.7
Σ AUC		24.41 10⁶	42.80 10⁶	53.40 10⁶

629 n.i.: no identified; AUC (area under curve)

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635 Figure legends

636 **Figure 1.** Levels of TNF- α , IL-1 β and IL6 secreted by THP-1/M activated with LPS in
637 presence of original extract and SAF fractions. Positive control: cells stimulated with LPS
638 but in absence of extract. Negative control: cells in contact just with RPMI media. Ind.:
639 Indomethacin. Original: original yarrow extract. P10: precipitation vessel fraction at 10
640 MPa. P15: precipitation vessel fraction at 15 MPa. S10: separator fraction at 10 MPa.
641 S15: separator fraction at 15 MPa. Each bar is the mean of three determinations \pm S.D.
642 *Denotes statistical differences when compares with positive control. ^{a,b,c,d} Different
643 lowercase letters indicate statistical differences between samples at 5 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$. ^{A,B,C,D}
644 Different capital letters indicate statistical differences between samples at 10 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$.
645 Significance level at $p \leq 0.05$ with Fisher's Least Significant Difference (LSD) test.

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660 Figure 1.

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